

Statistical literacy of Quilombola girls: The importance of considering funds of knowledge

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Quilombola communities are ethnic groups comprised of descendants of enslaved Africans, defined by criteria of self-attribution and validation. Becoming Quilombola women involves a sociocultural construction intersected by issues of gender, class and race, which demands the mobilization of funds of knowledge to organize and maintain life in their territories. This doctoral thesis project aims to analyse Quilombola girls' actions and reflections which relate their funds of knowledge and statistical knowledge. Theoretical approach is based on Gal's perspective of statistical literacy, and critical mathematics education. The study will be conducted in a Quilombola community in Brazilian northeastern region. Methodology will explore how statistical investigative cycle approach can empower girls towards to critical read and write the world.

Introduction

Quilombolas are “ethnic-racial groups according to self-attribution criteria, with their own historical trajectory, endowed with specific territorial relations, with a presumption of black ancestry related to resistance to the historical oppression suffered” (Decree n° 4.887, 2003). In Brazil, the rights of Quilombolas are guaranteed by the Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil (1988), as well as Quilombola school education that is provided for the National Curriculum Guidelines (Ministério da Educação, 2013a) and other national official documents. Despite these legal achievements, the preservation of the Quilombola cultural legacy is still not guaranteed.

Our study covers the issue of anti-racist mathematics school education in a Quilombola context, based on theoretical perspectives and research studies which problematize issues related to race, power, equity and social justice in mathematics education.

The perspective of critical mathematics education is committed to social justice and democracy, relying on critical education, represented more markedly by Freire (1972/1990), who advocates the transformation of reality and oppression by oppressed people themselves, through knowledge of reality, formulations, reflection-action-reflection and dialogic interactions.

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According to Forner et al. (2017), “even though Freire did not think about mathematics when developing his legacy, several of his elements have a direct relationship with the development of mathematics” (p. 755). Thus, in critical mathematics education there are categories that are concepts examined by Freire, such as criticality, dialogue, democracy, reading the world, autonomy, which are very important for our study and essential for the work developed with Quilombola girls in the realization of an investigation in your community/family.

Emerged in the 1980s, critical mathematics education highlights the political aspects of mathematics education, suggesting that teaching should be based on dialogicity, horizontality between teachers and students and the use of mathematical knowledge in reading the world, through critical inquiries, aimed at promoting changes for students and their social contexts (Frankenstein, 1998; Skovsmose, 2007).

Our study raises questions and reflections on the relationship between critical mathematics education, Quilombola school education and anti-racist education. When we relate these three educational perspectives, we launch propositions which can confront the questionable and combatable processes of selection, exclusion and segregation common to the mathematics education of people in vulnerable situations (Teixeira, 2014), especially those belonging to the black communities, including those in which people of Quilombola ethnic identity participate.

The study will be carried out in the Onze Negras Quilombola Community, located in the Northeast of Brazil and which is marked by female leadership (Cabo de Santo Agostinho, 2007). The study aims to analyse data and reflections produced in the Quilombola girls’ statistical investigations about women’s daily practices to organize and maintain lives in their territories. These investigations will be carried out from stages of the investigative cycle (Wild & Pfannkuch, 1999) in the perspective of statistical literacy (Gal, 2002). The approach to data production will also be problematized by the ideas of Funds of Knowledge (González et al., 2005; Gutstein, 2007).

Critical mathematics education, funds of knowledge, statistical literacy and empowerment the knowledge of black Quilombola women

Critical mathematics education explicitly considers the political, social, democratic and emancipatory dimensions of mathematical knowledge (Frankenstein, 1998; Gutstein, 2006; Skovsmose, 2001; Valero, 2017; Valoyes-Chavez, 2017). This approach helps us to see mathematics as a mediator to be utilized by people to organize thoughts and actions, to critically understand the socio-political aspects of their lives, and to improve their own cognitive, procedural and social skills.

The perspective of critical mathematics education can potentialize an enhancement of cultural experiences, practices and knowledge for the work of the mathematics educator, whose essential principle is the knowledge built and embodied in people and communities, which Gutstein (2007) calls original and sociohistorical:

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It involves how people understand their lives, their communities, power relationships, and their society. We also mean the cultural knowledge people have, including their languages and the ways in which they make sense of their experiences. Some refer to this as “indigenous knowledge,” “traditional knowledge,” “popular knowledge,” or “informal knowledge” (p. 110).

González (2005) argues that critical mathematics education should value the so-called funds of knowledge, which consist of bodies of knowledge, practices, skills and strategies existing in each family or community, which include mathematical knowledge. When investigating knowledge backgrounds, they associated them with teaching through an ethnographic project, which foresaw pedagogical changes in the teaching of mathematics, giving more meaning, encouragement and improvement in the quality of school learning.

In the context of our project, the Quilombola women of Onze Negras community are owners and generators of funds of knowledge, which they mobilize to organize, nurture and maintain lives. They are responsible for a vast number of practices and knowledge which are resistant to historical erasure (Carneiro, 2005; Njeri, 2019). Such knowledge cannot be ignored by the institutions that deal with those people, because such inconsideration perpetuates the epistemicide arising from colonialism, which is defined by Carneiro (2005) as:

one of the most effective and lasting instruments of ethnic/racial domination, due to the negation of the legitimacy of knowledge forms, knowledge produced by the dominated groups and, consequently, its members as subjects of knowledge (p. 96).

Skovsmose (2001, 2007) argues that for mathematics education to comply with democratic standards, it cannot be at the service of a power system that discriminates people by gender, race and social status, undermining their empowerment for citizen action.

According to Valoyes-Chávez (2017) “racial ideologies achieve fundamental functions in the reproduction of racial inequalities in the access to mathematical knowledge and in the construction of students’ mathematical identities” (p. 147). Thus, racial ideologies favour the naturalization of failures in relation to the domain of mathematical content conveyed in the teaching process of black students. In the field of mathematics education, it is essential to question how racial tensions are communicated in mathematics teaching processes.

Skovsmose (2007) emphasises that the students’ socio-political environments must be considered essential for the teaching and learning processes of mathematics. That kind of educational approach might help decentralizing the hegemonic power of teachers’ interests, because is based on an important democratic principle in which teachers and students play different but equally important roles in dialogue. Therefore, mathematics educators must continue “in search of ways to reconcile their classroom practice with struggles for social change” (Frankenstein, 1998, p. 116).

Gal (2002) argues that statistical literacy may be necessary for people and their communities in different ways, making them more aware of trends and phenomena of social and personal importance, as well as enabling them to face opportunities, public debates or actions in community. He proposes a theoretical model of statistical literacy involving elements of knowledge, which are literacy skills, statistical knowledge, mathematical knowledge, and dispositional elements, which relate to people’s critical stance, beliefs and

attitudes (Gal, 2002, pp. 2–3). In this research project, we focus on Gal’s perspective which emphasises the critical elements of statistical literacy. In addition, we will explore possibilities to challenge students to be co-investigators and question hegemonic ideologies, their contradictions and falsehoods, providing transformative learning experiences (Frankenstein, 1998). Thus, the perspective of statistical literacy is a process that can provide the basis for a critical social participation of individuals, not only with technical and conceptual knowledge of statistics, but also with subjective knowledge of individuals (Gal, 2002).

Monteiro and Carvalho (2021) state that “this perspective of statistical literacy, which promotes critical interpretations of this statistical information, is a very important social need, since it helps people to exercise their citizenship to the full” (p. 613).

In light of the statistical literacy model (Gal, 2002) and the perspective of Critical Mathematics Education (Frankenstein, 1998; Gutstein, 2006; Skovsmose, 2007; Valero, 2017; Valoyes-Chavez, 2017) we propose this study, in which girls of a traditional Quilombola community participate in activities within the investigative cycle, in which they will produce data on the knowledge of Quilombola women.

About Quilombos and Quilombola people

In Brazil, from the 16th to the 19th century, there were movements of struggle and Quilombola resistance against slavery, exploitation and the death of indigenous and African peoples. Quilombos were formed, territories organized and instituted with the objective of ensuring the existence of the insurgents. It is in this historical context that ethnic identity is also forged, which carries the power and strength to exist and resist in situations of profound dehumanization.

The Quilombola communities are comprised of people descended from a civilization which was originally prosperous in different ways. A large population that was disrooted from their mother continent, was slavered, and suffered genocide in the exile, but despite all managed to keep in their bodies, words and culture, the organization of Quilombola nations, *terreiros* (African-based collective religious spaces), movements and samba schools (Nascimento, 2002).

Currently, in Brazil and in other corners of the world, colonialism is maintained through racism that remains entrenched in social structures, which can be revealed in statistical data presented by several sources of information, in journalistic news and in the general media. Such statistical data reflect socioeconomic inequalities between different racial and ethnic groups, especially when referring to the reality of black women.

Our study is politically situated, when it turns to the reality of Quilombola women, in an investigation carried out by girls from this ethnic-racial group, as becoming a black and Quilombola woman requires learning that involves the struggle against a context of slavery, patriarchal tradition and classist, perpetuated by the oppression, exploitation and subordination of black bodies (Ribeiro, 2017).

According to Gomes (2020), when Quilombola women produce knowledge “they promote their emancipation and come to understand their vital force in the construction of

Quilombola identities, which assert themselves through daily struggles against all sorts of oppression” (Gomes, 2020, p. 11). This fight for the affirmation of their identities, for the organization, nutrition and maintenance of their people’s lives takes place in different territories, with women as major agents in facing the socioeconomic problems of their communities.

Despite advances in the field of law, Quilombola communities and social movements are permanently intensifying their resistance and struggles in order to overcome challenging situations. Education and epistemic productions are important action fronts for this political purpose. In Brazil, Law N° 10.639 (2003) stands out, which regulates the mandatory teaching of Afro-Brazilian History and Culture in the Basic Education curriculum, the National Guidelines for Education in Ethnic-Racial Relations (Ministério da Educação, 2013b), the Guidelines for Education Escolar Quilombola (Ministério da Educação, 2013c), the Statute of Racial Equality (Law 12.288, 2010), among other laws and policies carried out by the “Movimento Negro Educador” (Gomes, 2017).

It is known that every community possesses beliefs, practices, and knowledge, including mathematical knowledge. In this sense, we believe that there is a long history of deletion, silencing or intentional epistemic neglect of the Quilombola knowledge funds, which we seek to address in this research.

Research paths

Quilombola communities are historically sources of knowledge and sociocultural practices, while resist and struggle against domination, exploitation and scarcity of material resources for subsistence. Therefore, the “Onze Negras” Quilombola Community, whose leadership is female, is also based on this same purpose of organization, maintenance of its members and combating different forms of injustice, through the mobilization of ancestral knowledge cared for by older people and respected by the youngest.

The project will propose to a group Quilombola girls to be engaged in an investigative cycle process (Wild & Pfannkuch, 1999; Santana & Cazorla, 2020) which will produce statistical data related to funds of knowledge mobilized daily by Quilombola women to maintain life in their territory (Figure 1).

The research method will involve three main procedures. Initially, it will be developed analysis of educational documents which guide the teaching of mathematics and statistical topics at local Quilombola school. This documental analysis aims to identify which pedagogical approaches are suggested, as well as how are related to Quilombola culture and alignment with the curriculum guidelines for Quilombola school education (Ministério da Educação, 2013c).

A second methodological procedure will be associated with semi-structured interviews carried out with voluntary Quilombola women participants to identify funds of knowledge which may possibly involve the investigation carried out by female Quilombola students in the experience of the investigative cycle. One possible topic might be about food and traditional recipes. For example, the Mesa Ancestral (2019) published a report on traditional

Quilombola gastronomy in which a leader of Onze Negras community explained the knowledge taught by older Quilombola people to overcome hunger, as well as to enjoy food and to promote health:

When I was a child, for example, I learned that satisfying hunger depends on knowledge and getting hands-on. (...) We were worth more than there was in the garden, so it was quite common for my grandmother to take advantage of everything there. (...) Our great-grandparents taught us a lot that most people who live in big cities only hear from a doctor, for example, put crushed eggshell on top of the food (Mesa Ancestral, 2019).

Figure 1: Investigative Cycle. Adapted from Wild and Pfannkuch (1999).

A third procedure will be related to pedagogical meetings between the researcher with Quilombola girls to reflect and experience the statistical investigative cycle. The topic to be investigated will be related to cultural communitarian practices. The girls will be involved in a cooperative problematization in order to choose such a topic. The statistical data collected by the participants will be analysed and represented with the collaboration of researchers.

As part of research data analysis, we will identify and problematize knowledge and dispositional elements of statistical literacy (Gal, 2002) mobilized by the group of girls. These reflections will involve content analysis carried out by the researchers. The main results and reflections will be socialized with the community.

Preliminary considerations

Our study in progress has driven us to more questions and more reflections in mathematics education field, especially when we establish a relationship with anti-racist education and Quilombola school education. What mathematics education is being practiced in the classroom, from an anti-racist perspective? What parameters, references and educational

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practices in mathematics education are being built, taking into account education for ethnic-racial relations, provided for in Law 10.639 (2003)? Does the mathematics education experienced in Quilombola schools respect and reflect the culture of these people as provided for in the educational guidelines for Quilombola school education?

We know that cultural rights are integral to human rights. When access to cultural assets and the historical past of a people is denied, the relationship of domination and the practice of violation of human rights is perpetuated. Now, for Quilombola people, access to the past and ancestral knowledge means reflecting on oppression and claiming for rights and reparations.

Therefore, we believe that Quilombola girls, when reflecting on the statistical information produced in their investigative actions on the funds of knowledge and Quilombola women's sociocultural practices to organize and maintain community life, will possibly present dispositional elements related to racism, sexism and the ideas of emancipation. We also believe that critical statistical research, from the perspective of statistical literacy, is one of the possible ways of strengthening students from ethnic-racial communities, which, together with other educational ways, contributes to social change.

With our study, we also wish to contribute to the debate with the community of researchers in mathematics education, suggesting a critical analysis of the tensions historically built-in power relations, knowledge – especially mathematical knowledge – and Quilombola ethnic-racial communities.

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